

8-Theory on Anti Matter – Mirror Projections of Arbitrary Variations

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Abstract:

In this paper, an analysis of the anti-matter will be presented as part of a Lorentzian manifold, (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$. The manifold is a connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary. Analysis will be made based on the arbitrary variation term, which was partitioned and discretized in the thesis, $\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$ as part of the main equation of the framework, describing large-scale behavior of the manifold overtime. The reasoning behind the construction than reveals that the moment of asymmetry in the series, yielding an outward acceleration of the matrix.

Introduction

Recall that we can derive the nature of fermions and the quark model by allowing the series, which contain two distinct elements to vary. So overall we obtain eight threefold combinations of those elements. Therefore, even though the elements are varying the series could vanish. That is in agreement with a stationary Lorentz manifold. $M = M_0 \times R$. There could be however, another way to ensure a stationary Lorentz manifold. First, one will present the original development as was presented in the 8T thesis.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

$$\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$\mathbf{0}: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2 \quad (1.17)$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0 \quad (1.18)$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0 \quad (1.181)$$

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1 \quad (1.182)$$

$$\delta g_1(0) \delta g_2(Y) \delta g_1 \quad (1.183)$$

$$(1(e)1(e)1)$$

$$2(e)2(e)2$$

$$(221)$$

$$(112)$$

$$(211)$$

$$(122)$$

$$(212)$$

$$(121)$$

The development of those was presented in the 8T thesis; no elaboration will be made here. Now, we can partition the term presented in equation (1.16) in a different way, via its mirrored element that differ in sign.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta \exists g_1 = 0$$

$$\delta g_2 + \delta \exists g_2 = 0$$

By mirror, it means the same but opposite in sign. So the overall sum of the series will hold as zero. In the 8- theory framework, quarks are regarded as arbitrary amount of curvature on a manifold. Based on this view, anti-quarks are an arbitrary curvatures with opposite direction. Same magnitude just the inverse direction. So overall, that framework would allow the existence of anti-matter. That Is in agreement with quantum field theory and with the Dirac equation for spinors. In fact, the moment of singularity could be a result of the series not equal to zero.

$$\delta g \neq 0$$

The moment the series is not equal to zero than means that we have net curvature, or maximal curvature on the manifold, which will yield a negative extremum time invariant acceleration from it.

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

In other words, the moment of asymmetry in the series yielding net curvature on the manifold could be the reason for singularity and so called among the masses "big bang". Whether actual predictions could be made regarding the mathematical framework is unclear. As it is mathematical, we do not have the physical data. It is purely analyzing the meaning of the equation and the framework.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)